

Buoyancy-driven Convection in Adiabatic Horizontal Frontal Polymerization

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Motivation

Frontal polymerization results from the coupling between ***thermal autocatalysis*** and ***heat diffusion***.

- *Monomer:*
trimethylolpropane triacrylate (TMPTA)
- *Initiator:* Luperox 231

Motivation

Frontal polymerization provides a **greener** and more **efficient** route for the synthesis of materials.

LETTER

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0054-x>

Rapid energy-efficient manufacturing of polymers and composites via frontal polymerization

Ian D. Robertson^{1,2,7}, Mostafa Yourdkhani^{1,7}, Polette J. Centellas^{1,3}, Jia En Aw^{1,3}, Douglas G. Ivanoff^{4,4}, Elyas Goli^{1,5}, Evan M. Lloyd^{1,6}, Leon M. Dean^{1,4}, Nancy R. Sottos^{1,4}, Philippe H. Geubelle^{1,3}, Jeffrey S. Moore^{1,2} & Scott R. White^{1,3*}

Robertson *et al.*, *Nature*, 557 (2018), 223

2D one-step FP model* coupled to Navier-Stokes equations

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial t} + \underline{v} \cdot \underline{\nabla} M = D_M \nabla^2 M - k(T)M$$

$$\rho_0 c_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \underline{v} \cdot \underline{\nabla} T \right) = \lambda \nabla^2 T - \Delta H k(T)M$$

$$\rho_0 \left(\frac{\partial \underline{v}}{\partial t} + (\underline{v} \cdot \underline{\nabla}) \underline{v} \right) = -\underline{\nabla} p + \underline{\nabla} \cdot \underline{\underline{\tau}} + \rho(T) \underline{g}$$

$$\text{div } \underline{v} = 0$$

$$k(T) = k_{\text{eff}}^0 e^{-E_{\text{eff}}/(RT)}$$

$$\rho(T) = \rho_0 + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} (T - T_0)$$

$$\underline{\underline{\tau}} = \underline{\mu} \left(\underline{\nabla} \otimes \underline{v} + (\underline{\nabla} \otimes \underline{v})^T \right)$$

M → P

Monomer concentration: $M(x,z,t)$

Temperature: $T(x,z,t)$

Fluid velocity: $\underline{v}(x,z,t)$

Pressure: $p(x,z,t)$

Ambient temperature $T_0 = 293$ K

Effective rate constant $k_{\text{eff}}^0 = 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at T_0

Activation energy $E_{\text{eff}} = 85.0$ kJ/mol

Thermal conductivity: $\lambda = 0,100$ W/(m K)

Solution density at T_0 : $\rho_0 = 800$ kg/m³

Solution viscosity: μ

Specific heat capacity: $c_p = 600$ J/(K kg)

Monomer diffusion coefficient $D_M = 10^{-9}$ m²/s

Reaction enthalpy: $\Delta H = -75.0$ kJ/mol

*Volpert, *in Self-Assembly, Pattern Formation and Growth Phenomena in Nanosystems*, Springer (2006).

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$$\text{div } \underline{v} = 0$$

Monomer concentration: $M(x,z,t)$
 Temperature: $T(x,z,t)$
 Fluid velocity: $\underline{v}(x,z,t)$
 Pressure: $p(x,z,t)$

- Initial conditions $T_0 = 293 \text{ K}$
 $M_0 = 1 \text{ mol/L}$; no flow

- Adiabatic** boundary conditions

$$\underline{v} = 0 = \frac{\partial M}{\partial x} \quad x = 0, x = L_x; \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0 \quad x = L_x$$

$$\underline{v} = 0 = \frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \quad z = 0, z = L_z$$

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

Infinitely large viscosity (reaction-diffusion front)

degree of cure

$$\psi = \frac{(M - M_0)}{M_0}$$

Time = 40 s, propagation speed ~ 0.2 mm/s, width ~ 2 mm.
Regime with no thermal instabilities.

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

Time = 40 s, $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} = -0.05 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \text{ K})$

degree of cure

$$\psi = \frac{(M - M_0)}{M_0}$$

*Infinitely large viscosity
(reaction-diffusion front)*

$\mu_0 = 1.5 \text{ mPa}\cdot\text{s}$
 $L_z = 1.25 \text{ mm}$

Deformation of the front by buoyancy-driven convection arising from ***thermal gradients***.

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

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The reaction zone propagates as a **hot spot**.

$L_z = 1.25$ mm

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

The front reaches an **asymptotic dynamics**.

$\mu_0 \searrow$
 Convection \nearrow
 Deformation \nearrow

$L_z = 1.25$ mm

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

The front reaches an asymptotic dynamics, **two regimes** are observed depending on the viscosity μ_0

\bar{W} = steady deformation

$L_z = 1.25$ mm

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

The front reaches an asymptotic dynamics, **two regimes** are observed depending on the viscosity μ_0

$$L_z = 1.25 \text{ mm}$$

\bar{u}_{\max} = maximum horizontal flow velocity

\bar{V} = constant propagation speed

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

The front reaches an asymptotic dynamics, **two regimes** are observed depending on the viscosity μ_0

$$L_z = 1.25 \text{ mm}$$

	Viscosity range	\bar{u}_{max}	\bar{W}	\bar{V}
Region I	$\mu_0 \geq 3.3 \text{ mPa.s}$	μ_0^{-1}	μ_0^0	μ_0^0
Region II	$0.25 \text{ mPa.s} \leq \mu_0 \leq 1.8 \text{ mPa.s}$	$\mu_0^{-2/5}$	$\mu_0^{-4/5}$	$\mu_0^{2/5}$

Characteristic horizontal convective time scale:

$$t_c \sim \frac{\bar{W}}{\bar{u}_{max}} \sim \frac{\mu_0^{-4/5}}{\mu_0^{-2/5}} \sim \mu_0^{-2/5}$$

$\mu_0 \searrow$: flow and deformation \nearrow but $t_c \nearrow \Rightarrow \bar{V} \searrow$

Different from **isothermal autocatalytic fronts** where convection increases mass transfer rates.

Tiani, De Wit, Rongy, *Adv. Colloid Interf. Sci.* 225 (2018).

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

The front reaches an asymptotic dynamics, **two regimes** are observed depending on the **layer thickness L_z** (mm)

$$\mu_0 = 1.5 \text{ mPa.s}$$

1. Front propagation with constant viscosity

Summary

The front reaches an asymptotic dynamics with steady shape \bar{W} , constant speed \bar{V} , steady vortex

CONVECTION ↗

“PASSIVE” REGIME

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W} &\sim W_{RD} \\ \bar{V} &\sim V_{RD} \quad (\text{cf: reaction-diffusion}) \end{aligned}$$

$$u_{\max} \sim \frac{L_z^3}{\mu_0}$$

“ACTIVE” REGIME

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W} &\nearrow \\ \bar{V} &\searrow \end{aligned}$$

$u_{\max} \nearrow$ but more weakly
(smaller scaling exponents)

$\mu_0 \searrow$ or
 $L_z \nearrow$

2. Front propagation with varying viscosity $\mu = \mu_0 e^{C\psi}$

The viscosity increases with the degree of cure ψ .

When C increases, the deformation decreases and $\bar{V} \rightarrow V_{RD}$.

$$L_z = 1.25 \text{ mm}$$

$$\mu_0 = 1.5 \text{ mPa.s}$$

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cf: Gao, Paul, Chen, Hong, Chamorro, Sottos, Geubelle, PRL 130 (2023).

$C = 8.0$

- **Buoyancy-driven convection** arises from **thermal gradients** across polymerization front.
- Convection strengthens when the **monomers' viscosity** is decreased or the **layer thickness** increases.
- **Asymptotic dynamics** with constant deformation ($\bar{W} \nearrow$ with flow), constant speed ($\bar{V} \searrow$ with flow).
- Transition between a “**passive**” regime (RD + hydro) and an “**active**” regime (**chemo-hydrodynamic coupling**).
- Viscosity increasing during reaction: flow ahead of reaction zone.